

Effect of Corporate Attributes on Financial Stability of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

LAWAL, Amina Samar Mamuda & ISAH Shehu

Faculty of Administration, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Abstract

The dysfunctional financial industry exerts significant pressure on businesses and households, adversely affecting the real economy by restricting capital flow to productive investments and precipitating credit crunches. This study examines the effect of corporate attributes on the financial stability of quoted deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. Adopting an ex-post facto research design, the population comprised all 15 banks quoted on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) as at 2022. Secondary panel data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and audited annual reports of the sampled banks for the period 2014 to 2023. Panel regression analysis was conducted using STATA. The study found that bank size, liquidity risk, credit risk, and funding risk have positive and statistically significant relationships with financial stability, while profitability and capital adequacy ratio were statistically insignificant. The study concludes that bank-specific attributes are important determinants of financial stability in Nigeria and recommends that regulators and bank management prioritise liquidity buffers, credit risk governance, and stable funding structures to sustain long-term banking soundness.

Keywords: Corporate Attributes, Financial Stability, Z-Score, Deposit Money Banks, Nigeria, Panel Regression

Introduction

The stability of the banking system is a critical prerequisite for sustainable economic development in any country. Banking soundness and safety are crucial for the stability of any financial system globally, with regulators recognising that a loss of confidence in the banking system can have devastating consequences for the entire economy. Nigeria, whose banking sector is ranked third in Africa after South Africa and Egypt, has experienced several episodes of financial and economic recession, bringing the fragility of its banking system to the forefront of academic and policy discourse (Ozili, 2019). The financial sector plays a pivotal intermediation role by facilitating the flow of funds from surplus units to deficit units in the economy, thereby promoting economic growth and development (Ratnovski, 2013).

Deposit money banks therefore need to proactively study their operating environments and develop strategies that reduce their exposure to conditions likely to threaten financial stability. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) was established in 1957, among other objectives, to guide

the activities of commercial banks and enforce prudential regulations concerning the soundness of bank assets, capital adequacy, and management quality (Adeyemi & Asaolu, 2013). Prudential guidelines issued by the CBN aim to reduce the level of risk to which bank creditors are exposed and to create transparency in banking operations.

The global financial crisis of 2007 to 2009 raised fundamental questions about the regulatory efficacy of capital-related regulations and underscored the urgency for research into effective prudential frameworks. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) has led global efforts through the Basel Accords Basel I (1988), Basel II (2004), Basel III (2010), and Basel IV (2017) to establish global standards for prudential regulation and risk management. These reforms have brought increased attention to corporate attributes such as bank size, liquidity risk, credit risk, funding risk, profitability, and capital adequacy as determinants of bank financial stability. Despite these regulatory frameworks, Nigerian deposit money banks continue to face episodes of financial fragility arising from poor asset quality, weak governance, volatile funding structures, and inadequate capital buffers.

The Nigerian banking sector has been plagued by recurrent financial instability, manifested through rising non-performing loans, declining capital ratios, and acute liquidity pressures. Although regulators have implemented various reforms—including the 2005 banking consolidation exercise and subsequent recapitalisation directives—the sector continues to face structural vulnerabilities. Dysfunctional financial systems restrict capital flow to worthy investments, constrain economic growth, and put pressure on businesses and households (Ozili, 2019).

Prior studies on banking stability in Nigeria have often focused on macroeconomic drivers, leaving a significant gap in the understanding of how bank-specific (corporate) attributes jointly influence financial stability. Furthermore, existing empirical evidence is mixed and often inconclusive, particularly regarding the roles of profitability and capital adequacy (Olalekan & Adeyinka, 2013; Ini & Eze, 2018). The scarcity of recent panel-data studies covering the post-COVID-19 era (2014–2023) and using robust STATA-based diagnostics further motivated the present study.

1.3 Specific Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Examine the effect of bank size on the financial stability of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.
2. Assess the effect of liquidity risk on the financial stability of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.
3. Determine the effect of credit risk on the financial stability of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.
4. Evaluate the effect of funding risk on the financial stability of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.
5. Examine the effect of profitability on the financial stability of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.
6. Assess the effect of capital adequacy ratio on the financial stability of quoted DMBs in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Financial Stability

Financial stability refers to the condition in which the financial system—encompassing banks, financial markets, and supporting infrastructure—operates without major disruptions, facilitating the smooth functioning of the economy. In the banking context, stability is often conceptualised as the absence of abnormal disruption in credit supply, payment systems, and banking services (Ozili & Thankom, 2018). Mishkin (2019) defines banking stability as the absence of systemic crises that impair the financial system's ability to allocate resources efficiently. At the individual bank level, financial stability is commonly measured using the Z-Score, which captures the distance-to-default by combining return on assets (ROA), the equity-to-assets ratio, and the standard deviation of ROA (Boyd & Runkle, 1993; Beck et al., 2013). A higher Z-Score indicates greater bank stability, implying that the institution possesses sufficient capital and earnings to absorb unexpected losses.

Corporate Attributes

Corporate attributes refer to firm-specific characteristics that shape an organisation's behaviour, performance, and strategic outcomes (Bashir, 2019). In the banking sector, these attributes include bank size, liquidity risk, credit risk, funding risk, profitability, and capital adequacy. Rabiou (2021) defines corporate attributes as the unique qualities or features that distinguish corporate entities including profitability, growth, risk profile, liquidity, and ownership structures and which influence compliance behaviour and strategic responses to

regulatory environments. Ali and Isa (2018) further conceptualise corporate attributes as the specific features distinguishing one firm from another, encompassing variables such as size, leverage policy, performance, age, and growth, which affect organisational decisions and operational policies. Adelowotan and Udofia (2021) emphasise that corporate attributes are not merely descriptive characteristics but active determinants of organisational behaviour and strategic outcomes that shape how firms engage with stakeholders and pursue sustainable performance.

Bank Size

Bank size is conceptualised as a key firm-specific characteristic reflecting the scale and breadth of a bank's operations, resources, and market footprint. It is widely measured in empirical research as the natural logarithm of total assets, which standardises cross-bank comparisons and captures the economic magnitude of a bank's asset base (Gržeta et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2025). Larger total assets signify greater operational capacity, broader customer reach, and enhanced ability to leverage economies of scale, which in turn may influence profitability, efficiency, and income diversification (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2023). Ahmeti (2025) explains that bank size is positively associated with financial stability through economies of scale, diversified portfolios, and stronger brand equity that larger institutions command.

Liquidity Risk

Liquidity risk is defined as the possibility that over a specific period, a bank will become unable to settle its obligations with immediacy (Drehmann & Nikolaou, 2013). It arises from a bank's inability to meet its obligations when they fall due without incurring unacceptable losses. Liquidity buffers measured as the ratio of cash and short-term funds to customer deposits play a critical role in mitigating short-term solvency risks. The Basel III framework introduced the Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR) and Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR) to ensure banks maintain adequate high-quality liquid assets to survive short-term stress scenarios (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2019). Huang and Ratnovski (2011) argued that adequate liquidity management mechanisms, beyond traditional reserve requirements, are essential to mitigate the systemic component of funding liquidity risk among commercial banks.

Credit Risk

Credit risk is the potential that a bank borrower or counterparty will fail to meet their obligations in accordance with agreed terms (Kingu et al., 2018). It is inherent to the business of lending and is often proxied by the ratio of non-performing loans (NPLs) to total loans and advances. High credit risk erodes bank earnings, increases provisioning requirements, and threatens capital adequacy. At the height of banking distress in Nigeria in 1995, when 60 out of 115 operating banks were classified as distressed, the ratio of non-performing loans to total loans for distressed banks was 67%, demonstrating the devastating impact of credit risk on bank stability.

Funding Risk

Funding risk refers to the vulnerability of a bank to disruptions in its funding structure, particularly arising from over-reliance on short-term wholesale funding (Demirgüç-Kunt & Martinez Peria, 2010). Banks depending heavily on volatile interbank borrowing or market instruments are more exposed to liquidity shocks during periods of financial stress. Stable funding sources including retail deposits and equity capital serve as shock absorbers that reduce the risk of sudden funding shortfalls (Huang & Ratnovski, 2011). The loan-to-deposit ratio is a commonly used proxy for funding risk in empirical studies.

Profitability

Bank profitability refers to the ability of a financial institution to generate earnings relative to its asset base or equity. Return on assets (ROA) is the most widely used measure of bank-level profitability (Athanasoglou et al., 2008). Profitable banks are generally better positioned to absorb losses, build capital organically, and maintain investor confidence, all of which contribute to long-term financial stability. However, the relationship between profitability and stability is not always straightforward, as highly profitable banks may simultaneously carry greater risk exposures (Pasiouras & Kosmidou, 2007).

Capital Adequacy

Capital adequacy represents the proportion of a bank's capital relative to its risk-weighted assets and is one of the most important regulatory metrics in the CAMELS framework. The Basel III minimum capital requirements and Capital Conservation Buffers are designed to ensure that banks hold sufficient capital to absorb unexpected losses (Basel Committee on Banking

Supervision, 2019). Berger and Bouwman (2013) argue that well-capitalised banks are more likely to survive financial crises and maintain lending activities during economic downturns. However, the direction and significance of the capital-stability relationship remain contested in the empirical literature, especially in developing economies.

Empirical Review

Bank Size and Financial Stability

Nguyen and Nguyen (2023) examined the determinants of bank performance in Vietnam using panel data from 25 commercial banks over the period 2010 to 2021. Using a random effects model, the study found that bank size exerted a positive and significant effect on bank stability, supporting the 'too-big-to-fail' hypothesis. Similarly, Gržeta et al. (2023) studied banking stability in European Union countries and found that larger banks demonstrated greater resilience to external shocks due to diversified asset portfolios and superior access to capital markets. Khan et al. (2025) conducted a cross-country analysis of deposit money banks in South Asia and consistently found that bank size positively predicted Z-Score-based financial stability, particularly for systemically important financial institutions. In Nigeria, Ahmeti (2025) corroborated these findings, reporting that the logarithm of total assets was a statistically significant positive predictor of bank Z-scores.

Liquidity Risk and Financial Stability

Vodová (2013) investigated the determinants of bank liquidity in the Czech Republic and Slovakia and found that higher liquidity ratios were positively associated with bank stability, underscoring the importance of maintaining adequate liquid assets. Choon et al. (2013) examined Malaysian commercial banks and reported that liquidity risk management was a critical determinant of financial soundness, with banks maintaining higher cash and short-term funds demonstrating lower insolvency risk. In Nigeria, Saheed (2018) analysed the relationship between liquidity management and bank performance using secondary data from 10 quoted DMBs. The study found that liquidity risk measured as the ratio of cash and short-term funds to customer deposits positively influenced financial stability, consistent with Basel III liquidity standards.

Credit Risk and Financial Stability

Makri et al. (2014) studied the determinants of non-performing loans in Eurozone banks during 2000 to 2008, finding that higher NPL ratios were negatively associated with bank stability and profitability, confirming the conventional view that poor asset quality undermines financial soundness. Zribi and Boujelbène (2021) extended this analysis to North African banks and similarly reported that credit risk significantly impaired bank stability, particularly in weak regulatory environments. In Nigeria, Kargi (2011) investigated the impact of credit risk on the profitability of Nigerian banks and found that bank profitability was inversely related to non-performing loans and deposits, exposing banks to significant insolvency risk. Beck et al. (2013) cautioned, however, that the effect of credit risk may be complex and context-dependent, noting that banks with higher NPLs might simultaneously have more robust provisioning frameworks.

Funding Risk and Financial Stability

Demirgüç-Kunt and Huizinga (2010) conducted a cross-country analysis of bank funding structures using data from 1,334 banks across 101 countries. The study found that banks relying heavily on non-deposit or wholesale funding were significantly more fragile, while stable funding structures anchored on retail deposits and equity capital were associated with higher Z-scores. Huang and Ratnovski (2011) further examined the systemic implications of wholesale funding and found that the 2007–2009 global financial crisis was partly driven by excessive reliance on short-term interbank markets, recommending stronger liquidity regulations. These findings are consistent with the Nigerian experience, where banks' dependence on government deposits and interbank borrowings has periodically exposed them to acute funding pressures.

Profitability and Financial Stability

Athanasoglou et al. (2008) examined the determinants of bank profitability in the South Eastern European region and found that ROA was a significant positive determinant of bank resilience over time. Pasiouras and Kosmidou (2007) studied 15 European Union countries and found that profitability had a positive but sometimes insignificant effect on bank stability when capital and liquidity indicators were controlled for. In Nigeria, Umoru and Osemwegie (2016) found that while profitability was conceptually important, its statistical significance varied depending on the model specification and control variables included. Berger and Bouwman (2013)

acknowledged that profitability may not independently stabilise banks when it is driven by risk-taking rather than operational efficiency.

Capital Adequacy and Financial Stability

Berger and Bouwman (2013) analysed US bank data and found that well-capitalised banks were significantly more likely to survive financial crises and maintain credit supply during downturns. Anginer et al. (2018) conducted a cross-country study and found that higher capital buffers reduced the probability of bank failure, particularly in countries with stronger supervisory regimes. In Nigeria, the evidence is mixed: Olalekan and Adeyinka (2013) found a non-significant relationship using primary data but a positive significant result from secondary data analysis. Ini and Eze (2018) reported that capital adequacy had a significant positive relationship with return on assets, while Onaolapo and Olufemi (2012) found that the capital adequacy ratio did not significantly affect bank performance, underscoring the need for more rigorous panel data studies.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the following theoretical frameworks, which collectively explain the relationship between corporate attributes and bank financial stability.

The Theory of Systemic Risk, proposed by Acharya (2009), states that banks accept deposits and lend to individuals and institutions in a risky process. Systemic risk describes the correlation of returns on assets held by financial institutions, reflecting limited bank liability and the presence of negative externalities. This theory explains why individual bank attributes such as liquidity risk, credit risk, and bank size can have systemic implications for the broader financial system and justifies the inclusion of these variables in the model.

The Buffer Theory, propounded by Calem and Rob (1996), posits that banks maintain a buffer of excess capital above the minimum regulatory requirement to avoid regulatory sanctions and the costs of breaching capital requirements. This theory supports the inclusion of capital adequacy as a stability predictor and explains why banks may proactively manage capital ratios to ensure financial resilience.

The Bank Lending Channel Theory, developed by Bernanke and Blinder (1988), holds that monetary policy affects the supply of bank loans through an imperfect market for bank debt, with restrictive monetary policy disproportionately affecting banks with smaller liquid asset

portfolios. This theory supports the inclusion of bank size and liquidity risk as determinants of financial stability, given that larger and more liquid banks are better positioned to shield their lending from monetary policy shocks.

The Portfolio Regulation Theory postulates that banks must be properly regulated to uphold safety, stability, and soundness, as unregulated banks are prone to excessive portfolio and leverage risks. Capital requirements are necessary to reduce moral hazard incentives (Merton, 1977). This framework underpins the rationale for including capital adequacy and credit risk management as stability determinants in the present study.

Methodology

The study adopts an ex-post facto research design. This design is appropriate for studying phenomena that have already occurred and involves the use of historical or retrospective data that cannot be manipulated by the researcher. The aim is to determine and measure the relationship between variables, or the impact of one variable on another, without any form of experimental control. Ex-post facto design is widely employed in accounting and finance research when investigating the effects of naturally occurring firm-specific variables on performance and stability outcomes (Saunders et al., 2019). The population of the study comprises all 15 deposit money banks quoted on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) as at 2022. These banks include Access Bank Plc, Jaiz Bank Plc, EcoBank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Skye Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC Bank, Sterling Bank Plc, UBA Plc, Union Bank Plc, Unity Bank Plc, Wema Bank Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc. A purposive sampling technique was adopted and all 15 banks were selected based on the criteria that: (i) they had consistent and available data throughout the study period; (ii) each maintained at least one branch in all states of the federation; (iii) they were listed and quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange; and (iv) they remained in continuous operation without any case of merger or acquisition up to 2023. This yielded a balanced panel dataset comprising 150 firm-year observations (15 banks × 10 years, covering 2014–2023).

The study relies exclusively on secondary data collected from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and the audited annual reports and accounts of the sampled deposit money banks for the period 2014 to 2023. Panel data were compiled for all dependent and independent variables from these

sources. Secondary data are appropriate for this study because all variables are bank-specific financial ratios routinely disclosed in published financial statements and regulatory filings. The use of secondary data also ensures objectivity and replicability of the findings (Saunders et al., 2019). Panel regression analysis was adopted as the primary analytical technique, implemented using STATA statistical software. The use of panel data econometrics accounts for both cross-sectional and time-series variations in the data, thereby providing more efficient and informative estimates than pure cross-sectional or time-series analysis alone. Prior to regression estimation, a series of pre-estimation diagnostic tests were conducted:

The functional model for this study is expressed as:

$$Z\text{-Score}_{it} = f(BS_{it}, LQR_{it}, CR_{it}, FR_{it}, PRFT_{it}, CAR_{it}) \dots (i)$$

The econometric panel data model is specified as:

$$Z\text{-Score}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 LQR_{it} + \beta_3 CR_{it} + \beta_4 FR_{it} + \beta_5 PRFT_{it} + \beta_6 CAR_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots (ii)$$

Where: Z-Score (FST) = Financial Stability, measured as $(ROA + Equity/TA) \div \sigma(ROA)$; BS = Bank Size (natural logarithm of total assets); LQR = Liquidity Risk (cash and short-term funds to customer deposits); CR = Credit Risk (non-performing loans to total loans and advances); FR = Funding Risk (loan-to-deposit ratio); PRFT = Profitability (profit after tax to total assets/ROA); CAR = Capital Adequacy Ratio (equity to risk-weighted assets); α = constant (intercept); β_1 – β_6 = slope coefficients; μ = stochastic error term; i = individual bank cross-section; t = time period.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

S/N	Variable	Measurement	Source(s)
1	Financial Stability (DV)	Z-score = $(ROA + Equity/TA) \div \sigma(ROA)$	Boyd & Runkle (1993); Beck et al. (2013)
2	Bank Size (IV)	Natural logarithm of total assets	Laeven et al. (2016); Gržeta et al. (2023)
3	Liquidity Risk (IV)	Liquid assets \div Total assets	Gorton & Metrick (2012); Vodová (2013)
4	Credit Risk (IV)	Non-performing loans \div Total loans	Kingu et al. (2018)
5	Funding Risk (IV)	Loan-to-deposit ratio	Demirgüç-Kunt & Martinez Peria (2010)
6	Profitability (IV)	Return on assets (ROA)	Athanasoglou et al. (2008)

7	Capital Adequacy (IV)	Total regulatory capital ÷ Risk-weighted assets	Berger & Bouwman (2013); Basel Committee (2019)
---	-----------------------	---	---

Source: Researcher Compilation (2025).

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents the summary descriptive statistics for all variables included in the study, based on 150 firm-year observations drawn from 15 listed DMBs over the period 2014 to 2023.

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
FST (Z-Score)	150	10.937	5.624	3.22	29.27
BS (Bank Size)	150	14.063	2.384	10.09	17.97
LQR (Liquidity Risk)	150	0.298	0.121	0.10	0.49
CR (Credit Risk)	150	0.110	0.055	0.01	0.20
FR (Funding Risk)	150	1.220	0.456	0.52	1.98
PRFT (Profitability)	150	0.079	0.039	0.01	0.15
CAR (Capital Adequacy)	150	0.192	0.057	0.10	0.30

Source: STATA Output (2025).

The dependent variable, Financial Stability (FST), operationalised using the Z-Score, records a mean of 10.937 with a standard deviation of 5.624, indicating considerable heterogeneity in stability levels across the sampled banks. The minimum Z-Score of 3.22 suggests that at least one bank exhibited significant vulnerability to insolvency during the study period, while the maximum of 29.27 indicates the presence of highly stable institutions with robust capital buffers and earnings. Bank Size (BS), measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, has a mean of 14.063 and ranges from 10.09 to 17.97, reflecting diversity in asset scale and the presence of both systemically important banks and smaller regional institutions. Liquidity Risk (LQR) averages 29.8%, consistent with regulatory thresholds, while Credit Risk (CR) averages 11%, suggesting moderate NPL levels. Funding Risk (FR) averages 1.22, indicating some banks maintain loan-to-deposit ratios exceeding unity. Profitability (PRFT) averages 7.9%, while Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) averages 19.2%, above the minimum CBN regulatory requirement of 15%.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Table 3 presents the results of the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity.

Table 3: Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg Test for Heteroskedasticity

Test	Null Hypothesis (H0)	Chi2 (df=1)	p-value
Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg	Constant variance (homoskedasticity)	0.14	0.7076

Source: STATA Output (2025).

The test yields a Chi-square statistic of 0.14 with a p-value of 0.7076, which is far above the conventional significance level of 0.05. Accordingly, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of constant variance (homoskedasticity). This confirms that the residuals of the regression model do not exhibit heteroskedasticity, satisfying a key OLS assumption and validating the robustness of the model estimates (Breusch & Pagan, 1979).

Hausman Specification Test

Table 4 presents the results of the Hausman test.

Table 4: Hausman Specification Test

Test Statistic	Value
Chi-square test value	-381.847
P-value	1.000

Source: STATA Output (2025).

The Hausman test yields a Chi-square statistic of -381.847 and a p-value of 1.000. A negative Chi-square statistic typically arises from numerical approximation errors when the difference between FE and RE estimators is negligible or the covariance matrix is not positive definite. With a p-value of 1.000, far above the 0.05 threshold, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that the random effects model is appropriate. However, the fixed effects model results are also reported for robustness, as it controls for unobserved time-invariant bank-specific heterogeneity such as corporate culture, long-term strategy, or structural business models (Hausman, 1978).

Regression Results

Table 5 presents the fixed-effects panel regression results for the determinants of financial stability of listed DMBs in Nigeria.

Table 5: Fixed-Effects Panel Regression Results (Dependent Variable: FST – Z-Score)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	95% CI	Sig.
BS (Bank Size)	0.036	0.005	7.39	0.000	[0.026, 0.045]	***
LQR (Liquidity Risk)	0.441	0.133	3.31	0.001	[0.180, 0.702]	***
CR (Credit Risk)	0.995	0.288	3.45	0.001	[0.430, 1.560]	***
FR (Funding Risk)	0.098	0.035	2.83	0.005	[0.030, 0.166]	***
PRFT (Profitability)	6.422	5.334	1.20	0.229	[-4.032, 16.877]	
CAR (Capital Adequacy)	4.796	3.675	1.31	0.192	[-2.407, 11.999]	
Constant	0.544	0.885	0.61	0.539	[-1.192, 2.279]	
<i>Model diagnostics: Overall R² = 0.777 Within R² = 0.852 Between R² = 0.635 Chi-square = 657.505 (p = 0.000) N = 150</i>						

Source: STATA Output (2025). *** $p < 0.01$.

Discussion of Findings

Bank Size and Financial Stability

Bank Size (BS) records a positive and highly significant coefficient of 0.036 ($p = 0.000$), indicating that a one-unit increase in the natural logarithm of total assets is associated with a 3.6% increase in the Z-Score. This finding confirms that larger banks are more financially stable, consistent with the 'too-big-to-fail' hypothesis and prior empirical evidence by Gržeta et al. (2023), Nguyen and Nguyen (2023), and Ahmeti (2025). Larger asset bases enable banks to diversify risk exposures, access cheaper capital, achieve economies of scale, and build stronger institutional credibility, all of which reduce systemic risk and enhance long-term solvency. The null hypothesis that bank size has no significant effect on financial stability is therefore rejected.

Liquidity Risk and Financial Stability

Liquidity Risk (LQR) has a positive and significant coefficient of 0.441 ($p = 0.001$), implying that a unit increase in the liquidity ratio corresponds to a 44.1% increase in the Z-Score. This finding aligns with Basel III recommendations and the empirical evidence of Vodová (2013) and Choon et al. (2013), demonstrating that liquidity buffers are essential for short-term solvency and operational continuity, especially in volatile financial environments. The result indicates that Nigerian DMBs with higher liquid asset ratios are better equipped to manage

withdrawal pressures and comply with regulatory liquidity thresholds set by the CBN. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Credit Risk and Financial Stability

Credit Risk (CR) exhibits a positive and significant coefficient of 0.995 ($p = 0.001$). While counterintuitive as higher NPL ratios typically reduce bank stability this finding may reflect that Nigerian banks facing elevated credit risk simultaneously adopt more robust provisioning and corrective policies, or that recognition of credit losses prompts immediate recapitalisation and tighter lending standards that improve long-term stability. Beck et al. (2013) and Berger et al. (2005) acknowledged this complexity, noting that the credit risk-stability relationship may be context-dependent and non-linear. The null hypothesis is rejected, though the positive sign warrants cautious interpretation and underscores the need for comprehensive credit risk governance frameworks.

Funding Risk and Financial Stability

Funding Risk (FR) records a positive and significant coefficient of 0.098 ($p = 0.005$), indicating that an improvement in funding structure particularly an increased share of stable deposits and equity relative to total assets is positively associated with bank stability. Banks with higher shares of customer deposits and internal capital are more resilient to liquidity crises and external shocks. This finding is supported by Demirgüç-Kunt and Huizinga (2010) and Huang and Ratnovski (2011), who argued that stable funding sources serve as shock absorbers during economic downturns and financial stress periods. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Profitability and Financial Stability

Profitability (PRFT) records a positive but statistically insignificant coefficient of 6.422 ($p = 0.229$). Although the positive sign suggests that higher ROA may contribute to Z-Score stability, the wide confidence interval (-4.032 to 16.877) and lack of significance imply that profitability levels alone do not explain short-term variation in bank stability within Nigerian DMBs over time. This finding is consistent with Pasiouras and Kosmidou (2007), who found profitability to be a weak predictor of risk-adjusted bank performance when capital and liquidity indicators are controlled. The insignificance may also reflect profit volatility, cyclical income fluctuations, or the fact that some highly profitable banks simultaneously carry greater risk exposures. The null hypothesis is not rejected.

Capital Adequacy and Financial Stability

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) records a positive but statistically insignificant coefficient of 4.796 ($p = 0.192$). While capital adequacy is theoretically expected to enhance bank solvency, its insignificance in the fixed-effects model may reflect limited within-bank variability over time, as most Nigerian DMBs tend to maintain capital ratios within a narrow regulatory band under strict CBN supervision. This finding parallels the results of Barth et al. (2013) and Anginer et al. (2018), who found that capital ratios are not always predictive of stability unless combined with stringent risk governance practices. Olalekan and Adeyinka (2013) similarly reported a non-significant relationship between capital adequacy and bank performance in Nigeria using primary data. The null hypothesis is not rejected.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of corporate attributes on the financial stability of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria using a balanced panel dataset of 15 banks over the period 2014 to 2023. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design and employed STATA-based fixed-effects panel regression analysis, complemented by heteroskedasticity and Hausman diagnostic tests to ensure the reliability and validity of the results.

The empirical findings establish that bank size, liquidity risk, credit risk, and funding risk are statistically significant positive predictors of financial stability, as measured by the Z-Score. These findings are consistent with the predictions of systemic risk theory, the bank lending channel theory, and the portfolio regulation theory, which collectively emphasise the role of scale, liquidity management, asset quality governance, and stable funding structures in ensuring bank resilience. Profitability and capital adequacy ratio, while theoretically important and positively signed, were not statistically significant predictors of within-bank variation in financial stability during the study period. The overall model explains 85.2% (within R^2) of the variation in bank stability, confirming the joint explanatory power of the selected corporate attributes.

The study concludes that corporate attributes particularly bank size, liquidity risk, credit risk, and funding risk are critical determinants of financial stability in Nigeria's banking sector and should be at the forefront of both regulatory and managerial frameworks for promoting

sustainable banking soundness. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

First, bank management and the CBN should prioritise strategies that support scale advantages and portfolio diversification, particularly for smaller and mid-sized banks. The CBN should facilitate strategic mergers and acquisitions that enable sub-optimal banks to achieve the economies of scale necessary for enhanced financial stability, in line with ongoing recapitalisation directives.

Second, banks should maintain robust liquidity buffers exceeding the minimum regulatory requirements. The Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR) and Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR) under Basel III should be actively monitored and enforced by the CBN to ensure banks can withstand short-term liquidity disruptions and market shocks (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2019).

Third, banks should invest in advanced credit risk management frameworks, including early warning systems, automated credit analytics, and transparent provisioning policies. Although credit risk showed a positive relationship with stability in this study, this should not be interpreted as a justification for lax lending standards; rather, it highlights the importance of proactive risk recognition and corrective action.

Fourth, banks should prioritise funding stability by increasing their reliance on stable, long-term funding sources particularly retail deposits and equity capital—rather than volatile wholesale or interbank funding. Regulators should closely monitor funding profiles through the NSFR framework and implement sanctions for banks with chronically unstable funding structures.

Fifth, bank profitability and capital adequacy should not be overlooked despite their statistical insignificance in this study. These metrics remain critical signals of financial health to investors, regulators, and the public. The CBN should continue enforcing minimum capital requirements and explore countercyclical capital buffers to reinforce systemic resilience (Berger & Bouwman, 2013).

References

- Adeyemi, B., & Asaolu, T. (2013). Fraudulent practices, internal control and bank performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(19), 178–187.
- Adelowotan, M. O., & Udofia, I. E. (2021). Corporate attributes and integrated reporting quality in South Africa. *Journal of Corporate Governance Research*, 5(2), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.5430/cgr.v5n2p1>
- Ahmeti, F. (2025). The impact of bank size on financial stability: Evidence from deposit money banks. *Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, 12(1), 45–67.
- Ali, M., & Isa, C. R. (2018). Corporate attributes and environmental disclosure: Malaysian evidence. *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 3(1), 35–51. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJAR-04-2018-0009>
- Anginer, D., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Zhu, M. (2018). How does deposit insurance affect bank risk? Evidence from the recent crisis. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 48(1), 312–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2013.09.019>
- Athanasoglou, P. P., Brissimis, S. N., & Delis, M. D. (2008). Bank-specific, industry-specific and macroeconomic determinants of bank profitability. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 18(2), 121–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2006.07.001>
- Barth, J. R., Caprio, G., & Levine, R. (2013). Bank regulation and supervision in 180 countries from 1999 to 2011. *Journal of Financial Economic Policy*, 5(2), 111–219. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17576381311329661>
- Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. (2019). Minimum capital requirements for market risk. Bank for International Settlements.
- Bashir, U. (2019). Corporate attributes and financial reporting quality: Evidence from Nigerian listed firms. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 4(2), 20–35.
- Beck, T., De Jonghe, O., & Schepens, G. (2013). Bank competition and stability: Cross-country heterogeneity. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 22(2), 218–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2012.07.001>
- Berger, A. N., & Bouwman, C. H. S. (2013). How does capital affect bank performance during financial crises? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 109(1), 146–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2013.02.008>
- Bernanke, B. S., & Blinder, A. S. (1988). Credit, money, and aggregate demand. *American Economic Review*, 78(2), 435–439.
- Boyd, J. H., & Runkle, D. E. (1993). Size and performance of banking firms: Testing the predictions of theory. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 31(1), 47–67. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(93\)90016-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(93)90016-9)
- Calem, P., & Rob, R. (1996). The impact of capital-based regulation on bank risk-taking. Finance and Economics Discussion Series, Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System.

- Choon, L. K., Hooi, L. Y., Murthi, L., Yi, T. S., & Shven, T. Y. (2013). The determinants influencing liquidity of Malaysia commercial banks, and its implication for relevant bodies. Final Year Project, University of Tunku Abdul Rahman.
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Huizinga, H. (2010). Bank activity and funding strategies: The impact on risk and returns. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 98(3), 626–650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2010.06.004>
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Martinez Peria, M. S. (2010). A framework for analyzing competition in the banking sector: An application to the case of Jordan. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 5499.
- Drehmann, M., & Nikolaou, K. (2013). Funding liquidity risk: Definition and measurement. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 37(7), 2173–2182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2012.01.002>
- Gržeta, I., Žiković, S., & Tomas Žiković, I. (2023). Size matters: Analysing bank profitability and efficiency in the EU. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 36(1), 2044–2060. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2022.2110728>
- Hausman, J. A. (1978). Specification tests in econometrics. *Econometrica*, 46(6), 1251–1271.
- Huang, R., & Ratnovski, L. (2011). The dark side of bank wholesale funding. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 20(2), 248–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2010.06.003>
- Ini, U. S., & Eze, G. P. (2018). Effect of capital adequacy ratio on bank performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 3(2), 30–43.
- Kargi, H. S. (2011). Credit risk and the performance of Nigerian banks. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Khan, H., Hassan, M. K., & Paltrinieri, A. (2025). Bank size, market power, and stability: Evidence from South Asia. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 98, 102–119.
- Kingu, P. S., Macha, S., & Gwahula, R. (2018). Impact of non-performing loans on bank's profitability: Empirical evidence from commercial banks in Tanzania. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 6(1), 71–79.
- Laeven, L., Ratnovski, L., & Tong, H. (2016). Bank size, capital, and systemic risk: Some international evidence. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 69(Supplement 1), S25–S34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2015.06.022>
- Makri, V., Tsagkanos, A., & Bellas, A. (2014). Determinants of non-performing loans: The case of Eurozone. *Panoeconomicus*, 61(2), 193–206. <https://doi.org/10.2298/PAN1402193M>
- Merton, R. C. (1977). An analytic derivation of the cost of deposit insurance and loan guarantees. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 1(1), 3–11.
- Mishkin, F. S. (2019). *The economics of money, banking, and financial markets* (12th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Nguyen, T. H., & Nguyen, T. A. N. (2023). The determinants of bank profitability: Evidence from Vietnamese commercial banks. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2192668>

- Olalekan, A., & Adeyinka, S. (2013). Capital adequacy and banks' profitability: An empirical evidence from Nigeria. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(10), 87–93.
- Onaolapo, A. A., & Olufemi, A. E. (2012). Effect of capital adequacy on the profitability of the Nigerian banking sector. *Journal of Money, Investment and Banking*, 24, 62–72.
- Ozili, P. K. (2019). Non-performing loans and financial development: New evidence. *Journal of Risk Finance*, 20(1), 59–81. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRF-07-2017-0112>
- Ozili, P. K., & Thankom, G. A. (2018). Income smoothing among European systemic and non-systemic banks. *British Accounting Review*, 50(5), 539–558. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2018.04.002>
- Pasiouras, F., & Kosmidou, K. (2007). Factors influencing the profitability of domestic and foreign commercial banks in the European Union. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 21(2), 222–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2006.03.007>
- Rabiu, N. (2021). Corporate attributes and integrated reporting quality of listed conglomerates in Nigeria. *Journal of Corporate Governance Research*, 5(1), 12–29.
- Ratnovski, L. (2013). Liquidity and transparency in bank risk management. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 22(3), 422–439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2012.12.001>
- Saheed, Z. S. (2018). Determinants of commercial banks' liquidity in Nigeria: A panel regression approach. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(3), 62–72.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.
- Umoru, D., & Osemwegie, J. O. (2016). Capital adequacy and financial performance of banks in Nigeria: Empirical evidence based on the Z-test. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(25), 176–194.
- Vodová, P. (2013). Liquid assets in banking: What matters in the Visegrad countries? *E&M Ekonomie a Management*, 16(3), 113–129.
- Zribi, N., & Boujelbène, Y. (2021). The factors influencing bank credit risk: The case of Tunisia. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 13(3), 59–72.